

CHILDREN OF PRE-SCHOOL AGE FROM THE PHYSICAL ASPECT IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPMENT

F.Kh.Karimov

Tashkent Institute of Finance

Associate Professor of "Physical Culture And Sports" Department

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7855175>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 13th April 2023

Accepted: 21th April 2023

Online: 22th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Development, system, foundation, slowness.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the task of the educator in the physical development of children of preschool age is highlighted. Such systematic and complementary attention by the state to the preschool education system, which is considered the foundation of education, and practical help is provided in the article.

Complete education of children from 3 to 7 years old in the field of preschool education The head of our state considered the issue of ensuring pushed. The reason is that instead of performing the function of kindergartens as an educational institution, parents are at work that it has become a child-centered institution, low coverage, buildings in disrepair, used for other purposes, methodologically incomplete, pedagogues are social solving complex problems such as protection and low wages is an issue that cannot be delayed was Over the next 20 years, the number of state-owned preschools will increase to 45% the fact that only 818,000 of 2.45 million children are enrolled in kindergartens is proof of these ideas can be. The infrastructure and material and technical base of preschool educational institutions is unusable situation did not allow to ensure full coverage of children with pre-school education. Due to the laziness of some officials, it has been set for the development of the sector that the works were not completed on time, actions to open a private kindergarten that the construction work in the local kindergartens has not been fully completed Such shortcomings were followed by continuous errors. That's what learning is showed that the current system of preschool education management has existing problems timely detection and elimination, as well as further development of this field It was not possible to develop and implement innovative solutions for...

The meeting held on August 16, 2017 will remain in the history of the preschool education system. there was a meeting. On this day, the President of our country will strengthen the state national gene pool spoke about it and defined many directions for the development of the first stage of education. In particular, this is a radical structural reform of the pre-school education system institutions were assigned important tasks for full inclusion of children. Speaking about the education system, which is of decisive importance in our lives, Abdullah It is necessary to say again and again the wise thoughts of our grandfather Avloni: education is for us it is a matter of life and death," said the President. - No matter which field we take, we have modern mature personnel Without education, we cannot achieve any

change or a prosperous life. Such personnel, preparation of a healthy gene pool of the nation begins first of all with the preschool education system. Their thinking compared to a child who attended kindergarten and a child who did not attend kindergarten it is not difficult to notice that there is a difference between the earth and the sky That is why we state the issue of revision of the preschool education system we raised it to the level of politics and started great work in this regard. If you do this in every way if we don't do it carefully, we can achieve a quality change in the entire education system, education it will be difficult for us to ensure its continuity, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Above we have listed only some of them, to eliminate the problems that have not been seen from the beginning to the end As a first step, the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established. Adopted in order to eliminate existing problems in the reform of the preschool education system

The President's decision envisages the implementation of large-scale measures. Before school implementation of the unified state policy aimed at the development of the education system, the system Structurally, radical reform, management structure organization measures were determined. "The Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan organizes activities in accordance with the decision "on achieving" a new system was created in this field. The new ministry is tasked with developing a unified state policy in the field of preschool education and implementation, expansion of the state and non-state network of preschool educational institutions and strengthening the material and technical base, providing them with qualified pedagogical personnel, sharp increase in enrollment of children in pre-school educational institutions, education children by implementing modern educational programs and technologies intellectual, spiritual-aesthetic, physical development and the quality of their school preparation the tasks of radical improvement have been set, - says the Minister of Preschool Education Agrepina Shin. How much methodological support is necessary? The basis of any education is methodology, including and that of preschool education. New education in raising the quality of preschool education methods, innovative technologies are of great importance. The reason is material and technical of MTT although the base is high, if the educator does not work with the child, he will receive new information every day if he does not teach, the result of all actions will be zero. Experts in the field Pre-school education in order to improve their skills and provide them with the necessary methodical support retraining of leaders and specialists of institutions and improving their qualifications institute was established. To the issue of training specialized personnel in the field of preschool education special attention was paid. The one who implements all the decisions that are made, highly qualified to teach our children the most necessary life concepts and skills the issue of training educators was on the agenda. To modern requirements in this field development of advanced pedagogic methods and techniques, teaching and learning-methodology creating and publishing a new generation of literature was also a very urgent task. Uzbekistan The Republic of the Republic of Kazakhstan is committed to the development of children of primary and preschool age requirements and the State curriculum of "Ilk Kadam" preschool educational institution was adopted. Now the educators of the modern preschool education organization have set the children free is teaching new information through game training in activity centers. It is necessary to take into account the age and physiological condition of more children in pre-school education

should not be forgotten. Get active using simple, easy, and low-time play exercises working in the centers will give good results. More connected with the environment training children's mind, worldview, free thinking, expressive skills, independent develops work skills, that is, life competence.

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